

of low herbage yields in acid sulfate areas. Herbage cutting did not significantly affect grain yield and yield components.

Plant height and dry matter production were significantly decreased by herbage removal. Fertilizer application

and increased cuttings may improve the relatively low herbage yield and make it more economical. □

Integrated pest management—diseases

Growth and sclerotial production of *Sclerotium oryzae* on different media

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S. oryzae was grown on 15 natural and synthetic media in petri plates to test their growth and production of sclerotia. Fungus colony diameters were measured after 5 d of incubation. Petri plates were further incubated to observe sclerotial production. The plates were examined every 5 h to study sclerotial characters.

Average growth was maximum on potato dextrose agar and minimum on Backman and Kabana's medium and Brown's agar (see table). All of the media except Backman and Kabana's medium and Neurospora V synthetic medium produced sclerotia.

The results showed no correlation among the radial growth of fungus, time of initiation, color, size, arrangement, and average number of sclerotia per plate. □

Effect of different media on growth and sclerotial production of *S. oryzae*.

Medium	Av colony diam ^a (mm)	Time until sclerotial initiation (h)	Arrangement of sclerotia	Color of sclerotia	Size of sclerotia ^b (µm)	Av sclerotia/plate (no.)
Backman and Kabana's medium	26.7	-	-	-	-	-
Brown's agar	26.7	170	More toward periphery, less toward center	Black	249.37	4875
Corn meal agar	50.7	120	More toward periphery, less toward center	Black	266	13455
Czapek-Dox agar	63.3	125	Equally scattered	Brownish black	248.90	17550
Dextrose marmite agar	46.7	170	Equally scattered	Shiny black	266	1346.5
Neurospora V synthetic medium	35.7	-	-	-	-	-
Nutrient glucose agar	51.3	125	Equally scattered	Black	274.86	40755.5
Oatmeal agar	65	145	More toward periphery, less toward center	Black	248.26	17225.5
Peptone sucrose agar	51.3	130	More toward periphery, less toward center	Black	248.30	41471.5
Potato carrot agar	46.7	120	Equally scattered	Shiny black	274.86	45882
Potato dextrose agar	73.3	120	Equally scattered	Shiny black	274.86	45882
Radish root extract agar	30	145	Equally scattered	Brownish black	268	23075
Rice polish agar	41.3	125	Equally scattered	Black	294.30	12490.5
Richard's agar	36.7	130	More toward periphery, less toward center	Black	248.90	21650
Sach's agar	35	125	Equally scattered	Black	230	12255.5

^aAfter 5 d, based on 3 replications. ^bAv of 100 sclerotia. ^cLSD value of average colony diam (mm) at 5% = 3.98. CV = 5.27.

Effect of humic acid (HA) on severity of rice blast (BI)

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We studied the effectiveness of graded levels of HA extracted from lignite on the severity of BI in rice varieties IR50 (highly susceptible) and IR20 (moderately resistant) under greenhouse conditions.

HA powder at the rate of 0, 10, 20, 30, and 40 kg/ha was dissolved in the required quantity of 0.01 N KOH to obtain pH 7.2. These solutions were then mixed thoroughly into pots that

Effect of humic acid level on B1 incidence.^a

HA level (kg/ha)	IR50			IR20		
	Mean disease incidence (%)	Angular transformed value	Decrease from control (%)	Mean disease incidence (%)	Angular transformed value	Decrease from control (%)
0	51.3	45.7	-	27.8	31.8	-
10	25.2	30.1	33.5	15.5	23.2	27.3
20	22.3	28.2	38.3	13.3	21.3	33.0
30	36.5	37.2	18.7	19.7	26.4	17.2
40	40.9	39.8	13.1	22.4	28.2	11.3

^aMean of 3 replications.

already had the recommended dose of fertilizer. Seedlings were transplanted; treatments were replicated three times.

At 50 d after sowing the plants were artificially inoculated with the B1 pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav.

Disease incidence was assessed using a score chart of 0-9.

HA application reduced B1 severity. Reduction was maximum with 20 kg/ha. □